

THz antennas a vision of next generation wireless communications: a technical review

Sneha Moghe, Shri G.S Institute of Technology and Science, Indore.
Leeladhar Malviya, Shri G.S Institute of Technology and Science, Indore.

ABSTRACT

Terahertz (THz) frequency is becoming a new hot topic for researchers and scientist as it seemed to be the best solution for solving various problems occurring in its previous technologies like 4G and 5G. THz band lies in between microwave and infrared regions and was previously defined for the frequency range 0.3 - 3 THz. High spectral efficiency, large bandwidth, low diffraction and non-ionizing nature are the few characteristics of THz frequency band which has increased its demand in security, medical and detection of explosives etc. Metals and dielectrics like copper, CNT, Graphene, silicon, quartz and polyimide are some commonly used substrates for THz antennas and are briefly discussed in this paper. The paper provides a detailed study of various types of antennas commonly employed at THz frequency. High gain and efficiency are achieved by using MIMO antennas. Different fabrication techniques based on electronics and photonics for the generation of THz signals are also discussed in paper.

Keywords:

Graphene, ECC, SAR, SPP, TARC, THz

1. INTRODUCTION

A large amount of data is transmitted through wireless communication by means of light, sound, magnetic or electric fields. Out of all these possible ways radio waves proved to be the most popular solution for wireless transmission. The signals are transmitted in the form of electromagnetic energy. It incorporates the short as well as long distance communication through mobiles, Bluetooth and two way radios etc. Wireless mobile communication is classified into different categories based on telephone network standards named as generations where each generation is having more advance features in comparison to its previous generation.

The data rate and bandwidth were further improved in third generation (3G) and becomes 2 Mbps and 2 GHz respectively to fulfil the demands of high speed internet and worldwide roaming [2]. Fourth generation (4G) was based on IP packet switching technology to increase the number of multiple users in a single cell with channel bandwidth upto 40 MHz [3]. 4G technology provided better coverage and high quality video calling at very low data rates. It employed WLAN, WiMAX and LTE technologies for 700, 850.0, 950.0, 1800.0, 1900.0, 2100.0, 2300.0, 2600.0 and 3500 MHz etc, frequencies [4, 5].

5G works on data rates higher than 1 Gbps and bandwidth upto 28 GHz. The bands from 3.3-4.2 GHz and 4.4-4.99 GHz cover the lower frequency spectrum of 5G and higher frequency bands covers frequency range like 24.25-27.5 GHz, 26.5-27.5 GHz, 26.5-29.5, 27.5-28.28 GHz, 27.5-28.35 GHz, 37.0-40.0 GHz and 37.0-43.5 GHz which are employed by china, korea, japan etc. Bands covering frequencies greater than 60 GHz are given by 53.3-66.5 GHz, 55.4-66.6 GHz, 56.6-64.8 GHz, 57.0-64.0 GHz and 57.0-65.0 GHz [6, 7, 8]. Coverage is the major

issue in 5G systems mostly in rural areas as it needs large number of towers in comparison to 4G. Its speed is upto 10 Gbps which occupies lots of memory space in mobile phones and tends to enhance the size of battery which results in high power dissipation than its previous technologies. Hence, in order to find the solutions over these problems arises in 5G, THz frequency band came in existence as new frequency range for future wireless communication. As it is seen that data rates are doubled for every eighteen months proposed by Edholm's law [9]. In 1974, THz was described as the amount of frequency covered by Michelson Interferometer [10]. It covers the frequency range from 0.1 - 10 THz [11].

The bands above and below the THz spectrum are extensively studied but this band is still least investigated. Electronics and photonics are two different technologies which can be used for its generation. THz frequency band proved to be very efficient in data rate, bandwidth and efficiency which is compared with all its previous technologies in the Table 1.

THz signal can be generated by converting optical signal into THz signal. Optical signal may be in the form of pulse or continuous wave, where pulse signal of femtosecond laser pulses into nonlinear optical material. Continuous THz waves are generated by using optical parametric process in non linear materials like cdTE, Gap and ZnTE. The generation of THz signal is shown in Fig.1 [12].

Table 2: Comparison of previous generations with THz

Ref	Gen.	1G	2G	3G	4G	5G	6G (THz)
[1,2]	Key features	Mobility	Security	Better internet facility	Improved broad band service	Better coverage	High data rate and high penetration
[1,2]	Data rate	2 Kbps	64 Kbps	2 Mbps	1 Gbps	Higher Than 1 Gbps	10 Gbps
[1,2]	Spectral Efficiency (b/s/Hz)	.0015	0.16	0.8	1.46	2.84	0.1 Gbps per GHz
[1,2,3,4]	Applications	Voice Communication	Voice Call and text and picture message	Wireless voice communication and video calling	High Speed Internet and video conferencing	Provides IOT and AI based imaging applications	Security And
[1,2,3,4]	Disadvantages	Poor Voice quality	Signal loss in Case of 3G poor network	Require Expensive Compatible handsets	Users always needs hotspots and local networks	Network issues in rural areas	Difficult to use and health
[1,2]	Band width	2.4 KHz	64 KHz	2 MHz	1 GHz	>1 GHz	> 10 GHz

Figure1. THz signal generation process

2. METALS AND NON METALS AT THz

There are so many metals and dielectrics which play a very important role for making efficient THz devices. Some commonly used dielectrics are discussed in this section. Copper is a metal which is mostly used for designing antennas at RF and microwave frequencies. Antennas are suffered from conductor loss on using copper because of rough surface of copper at the interface of substrate and conductor resulting in low efficiency [13]. It is good conductor of electricity, so according to faraday’s law an electric field induced inside a current carrying conductor is expressed by equation (1).

$$\Delta \times E = \frac{\partial E}{\partial t}$$

Where, E is the electric field induced in a conductor with respect to time t.

At high frequencies current flowing through a conductor is sinusoidal so current density is mostly on surface of conductor. It is zero in the middle portion of the conductor. Metals are generally not taken as substrates at THz frequency, because of high values of power dissipation and skin depth

Graphene ($\epsilon_r = 4$ and $\tan \delta = 0.36$) has unique surface Plasmon Polariton property (SPP) and it shows quite high performance at THz frequency [14]. It proved to be the most appropriate material used for fabricating antennas at THz frequency. It posses very high mobility in comparison to silicon and III to V semiconductors. It consist of carbon atoms in sp^2 hybridization where bonding between atoms is done by means of σ and π bonds. The surface conductivity of Graphene is defined by intraband and interband conductivities and was given by the kubo formula. Expressions for the intraband and interband conductivities are defined by equations (2) and (3) [15].

$$\sigma_{intra} = j \frac{e^2 K_B T}{\pi h^2 (w + j\tau^{-1})} \left[\frac{\mu_c}{k_B T} + 2 \ln(e^{\frac{-\mu_c}{k_B T}} + 1) \right]$$

$$\sigma_{inter} \cong \frac{j e^2}{4\pi h} \ln \left(\frac{2|\mu_c| - w_h}{2|\mu_c| + w_h} \right)$$

Where, e is the charge of an electron, w is the radian frequency, h is plank’s constant, k_B is boltzmann’s constant, T is temperature, μ_c is the chemical potential and τ is the momentum relaxation time.

CNT are invented by Lijima in 1993. It is basically tubes of carbon having very small diameter in nanometers range. CNT has high efficiency and low radiation losses at THz frequency due to less skin effect. CNT has good electrical conductivity and slow wave property which makes it more suitable than copper. CNT and Graphene are used as nanocomposites. As CNT contains graphite layers of large length and surface area and having high conductivity which leads its use as filler in industries [16]. A comparison between copper, Graphene and CNT on the basis of different properties is given in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparison of material properties of copper, Graphene and CNT at THz

Ref	Parameter	Copper	Grapene	CNT
[3,13]	Mobility	$32 \text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{S}^{-1}$	$2 \times 10^5 \text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{S}^{-1}$	$8 \times 10^4 \text{cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{S}^{-1}$
[13,14]	Current density	10^6A/cm^{-1}	10^9A/cm^{-1}	10^9A/cm^{-1}
[3,14,15]	Thermal conductivity	$400 \text{Wm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$	$5000 \text{Wm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$	$3000 \text{Wm}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$
[14,15]	Tensile strength	587Mpa	1.5Tpa	50-500Gpa
[13,15]	Radiation loss	High	Low	Low
[2,14,16]	Efficiency	Low	High	High

Si ($\epsilon_r = 11.68$ and $\tan \delta < 4 \times 10^{-5}$ at 1 THz) is most widely used dielectric material due to its less lossy nature, moderate to high values of dielectric constant, easily etching capabilities, and stability over wider frequency ranges. Its absorption coefficient is less than 0.05cm^{-1} in

the THz range. The maximum radiation efficiency is achieved for the dielectric materials having low values of loss tangent and high values of relative permittivity at THz frequency. The SiO₂ and quartz are preferred substrates for large bandwidth applications due to their low relative permittivity [17, 18].

PDMS ($\epsilon_r = 2.35$, and $\tan\delta = 0.04$) is used in THz devices because of low cost, easy fabrication and having the ability to withstand temperatures between -50^o to 120^o C with moderate dissipation [19]. Experiments shows change in its various properties like young's modulus and strength for its thickness of 200 μ m [20]. Polyimide ($\epsilon_r = 3.24$ and $\tan\delta = 0.031$) are polymer containing two acyl groups bonded with nitrogen. It is most commonly used substrate for the fabrication of THz devices due to high mechanical stability. They are widely used in making metamaterials and in solar cells because of their flexible nature and operatibility between -269^oC to 400^oC temperatures [21]. They can be used as an insulating material and in coating of optical fibres.

Parylene ($\epsilon_r = 2$ and $\tan\delta = 0.04$) is thermoplastic having one of its type called as parylene C. Mostly used to provide insulation for electronic circuits from corrosion and other atmospheric changes. It is used at THz frequencies due to low loss and can withstand high temperature (-200^o C - (200^o) C [22]. Benzocyclobutene (BCB) is a thermosetting resin widely used for providing insulation because it is stable at high temperatures. As photosensitive BCB 4026-26 and non-photosensitive Cyclotene 3022-46 have relative permittivity and loss tangent in the range 2.41-2.65 and 0.002-0.009 at 1 THz [23]. Cyclic olefin copolymer (COC) is a new copolymer having low loss at entire THz frequency band [24]. Its loss tangent is 7×10^{-4} at 1 THz which is very low. Due to high chemical stability and low value of loss tangent it is used as substrate in antennas and microstrip lines.

3. FABRICATION TECHNOLOGIES OF THz ANTENNAS

Various technologies are present for the fabrication of antennas working at THz frequency. These are discussed here in details for the fabrication of antennas. Silicon germanium (SiGe) technology is the most preferred technology of all designers for making RF and microwave antennas as due to its various features like high gain, low noise, low cost and good power handling capabilities. Presently SiGe technology is used for the development of heterojunction bipolar transistors (HBT) with transistor cut off frequency $f_T > 300$ GHz and $f_{max} > 500$ GHz [25], and 3 dB bandwidth of 27 GHz [26].

GaN is mostly used for applications of high power. High electron mobility transistors (HEMT) were designed with $f_T > 450$ GHz, oscillation frequency of $f_{max} > 600$ GHz with breakdown voltage of $V_T > 13$ V [27]. Microwave monolithic integrated circuits based on GaN show an output power of greater than 2.1 W at 100 GHz for 4 GHz frequency range [28, 29]. Terahertz monolithic integrated circuit (TMIC) amplifiers are built using InP technology

having cut off frequency $f_T > 600$ GHz and maximum oscillation frequency of greater than 1.2 THz [30].

Photodiodes and quantum cascade light amplification of stimulated emission of radiation (LASER) are used as a local oscillator for generation of THz frequencies in heterodyne THz generation systems [31]. Presently compact signal generators and detectors are based on high electron mobility transistors (HEMT) on semiconductors like GaN and GaAs [32, 33]. Excitation of plasma waves is performed in the channel of HEMT by means of optical or electrical pumping methods.

Graphene is known as "the wonder material" and was invented in 2004 [34, 35]. It is a 2D material having honeycomb lattice like structure of carbon atoms. Graphene in the form of sheet and is called Graphene nanoribbons (GNR), which is used to make optical detectors due to its very high carrier mobility. Due to presence of SPP characteristics it is used to built nano antennas having very less magnitudes in comparision to THz antennas.

4. ARRAY AND MIMO ANTENNAS AT THz BAND

An array is a combination of several antennas called elements working like a single antenna for transmitting and receiving radio signals. Besides having low complexity SISO has few drawbacks in terms of interference and bandwidth in comparison to multiple input and multiple output (MIMO) systems [36]. Data rate and bandwidth of MIMO antenna seems to be very high due to multiple antennas for transmission. MIMO propagates the signal through multiple paths and provides better spectral efficiency for non line of sight communication [37, 38, 39]. Mutual coupling between MIMO antennas can be reduced by using various isolation techniques like polarization or space isolation [40, 41]. The capacity of MIMO is calculated by equation (4).

$$C = \log_2 \left(I_N + \frac{P}{N N_t} H H^* \right)$$

where, I_N is identity matrix, P is signal power, N is noise power, N_t and N_r are the number of transmitting and receiving antennas, H is channel matrix, and H^* is transpose of channel matrix respectively.

Various parameters are calculated for MIMO antenna in terms of scattering parameters and field equations to analyze its performance. ECC shows the amount of correlation between the radiation patterns of different antennas. Its value is zero if the two antennas radiates in opposite directions to each other i.e. they are uncorrelated. The maximum value of ECC for MIMO antenna is always less than 0.5 [42, 43, 44]. It is calculated by equation (5) [45].

$$ECC = \frac{|S_{11}^* S_{22} + S_{21}^* S_{12}|^2}{(1 - (|S_{11}|^2 + |S_{21}|^2))(1 - (|S_{22}|^2 + |S_{12}|^2))}$$

Where, S_{11} and S_{22} are the reflection coefficients at ports 1 and 2 and S_{12} and S_{21} are isolation between the ports.

TARC is defined as the ratio of incoming power to the power that is reflected back and it validates the values of S parameters [46]. Its value should be minimum as zero or one to show that maximum power is radiated and is calculated for two ports by equation (6) [47].

$$TARC = \frac{\sqrt{(|S_{11} + S_{12} e^{j\theta}|^2)(|S_{21} + S_{22} e^{j\theta}|^2)}}{\sqrt{2}}$$

MEG is expressed as the ratio of powers received by diversity antenna with respect to isotropic antenna [48]. Its value should be less than 3 dB for two ports. For two ports MEG1 and MEG2 are given and the MEG for MIMO or multiport is given by equation (7).

$$MEG = \frac{MEG1}{MEG2}$$

where, MEG1 and MEG2 are given by equations (8) and (9) for two ports.

$$MEG1 = 0.5[1 - |S_{11}|^2 - |S_{12}|^2]$$

$$MEG2 = 0.5[1 - |S_{12}|^2 - |S_{22}|^2]$$

DG shows the improvement of signal to noise ratio of MIMO in comparison to SISO. Ideally it should be equal to 2. It is calculated for 2 × 2 MIMO antenna as equation (10).

$$DG = 10\sqrt{1 - |ECC|^2}$$

CCL gives the information about the capacity of the channel upto which transmission of signal can be done successfully. The value of CCL should be less than 0.5 bits/sec/Hz. It is calculated by equation(11).

$$CCL = -\log_2 \text{Det}(\vartheta^R)$$

where, ϑ^R is calculated as in equation (12)

$$C = \begin{bmatrix} \vartheta_{11} & \vartheta_{12} \\ \vartheta_{21} & \vartheta_{22} \end{bmatrix}$$

5. SPECIFIC ABSORPTION RATE

When human body exposed to RF frequency then energy is absorbed by the tissues of the human body and is calculated in terms of specific absorption rate (SAR) [49]. Its unit is watts/kilogram [50]. The relation of SAR for electromagnetic energy is given by equation (13) [51].

$$SAR = \frac{\sigma E_i^2}{\rho}$$

Where, σ is the electrical conductivity in S/m, E_i is the electric field in V/m, ρ is the density of body tissue in kg/m³.

There is also change in temperature of human body when it gets exposed to radiations, for some time duration. This temperature change also gives the value of SAR which is calculated by equation (14) [52].

$$SAR = C \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t}$$

where, ΔT is the change in temperature, Δt is the time of exposure, C is the specific heat capacity of the tissue medium in J/K.

There are several techniques like compensation technique, field cancellation techniques and rod reflectors adapted for SAR reduction. Many multinational companies as nokia, ericsson and siemens used copper for reducing SAR values to 10% [53]. Aluminium proved to be better than copper as it decreases SAR value by 20% as well as it is free from corrosion. Perfect electric conductor (PEC) combined with silicon gives 40% SAR reduction [54] while graphite and carbon are also used for the same purpose. Ferrite sheets dissipates radiation so, they are used with monopole antennas to reduce absorbed power. Metamaterials are also used to reduce SAR as it stops particular frequency band and used in different structures like split ring resonator(SRR), open split and spiral resonators where each reduces SAR to 50% [55]. Nanomaterials like CNT, Graphene and its composites are proved to be ideal material for SAR reduction [56]. Different materials used as a shielding material are given in the chart in Fig. 2 [57].

Figure2. SAR reduction using different shielding materials

Radiation produced by wireless local area networks is very harmful for the brain and behavior of human and causes bad effects on the fertility [59]. The study showed that exposure to radiations causes bad effects on the head, increases the possibility of brain tumor [60]. In body worn antennas, SAR is a main concern, where antennas are used with electronic band gap which reflects the radiation back to reduce the undesired radiations [61].

6. VARIOUS APPLICATIONS OF THz ANTENNAS

1. cancer detection using THz antennas

THz frequency band poses so many attractive features. Its one of the main feature is that it can easily penetrate through fabrics and plastics. So it is mostly used for searching of bombs and concealed weapons. Because of its unique properties this band is used for diagnosis of various deceases. Recently breast cancer is most common decease in female and early detection reduces cost and also makes the treatment easier [62].

An antenna integrated with CSRR was developed for detection of breast cancer. The dielectric properties of

breast with tumor with normal breast are compared with each other having relative permittivity's 3.18 and 2.41 respectively and an impulse response of antennas are observed for the two cases. The simulation was done using phantom model of human breast. In the experimental set up, THz pulse taken as an input and results in case of tumor and without tumor are shown in Figs 3 (a), (b) and (c) respectively.

Figure 3. a) Antenna with CSRR b) without tumor c) with tumor

2. THz antennas for wireless communication

It is expected that in 2022 wireless traffic will consume 254 petabytes per month and due to rapid progress in multimedia services communication at THz frequency is gaining so much attention [64, 65]. In order to improve gain an 2×2 MIMO antenna having size $1430 \times 1400 \times 100 \mu\text{m}^3$ was designed on RT5880 substrate which gives 95 % efficiency over all the frequency band and gain of 8.69 dBi and 7.4 dBi at resonating frequencies of 0.292 THz and 0.231 THz respectively. Bandwidth and return loss were improved by providing inset feed which provides better impedance matching. The schematic view and return were shown in the Figs 4 (a) and (b) below [66].

Figure 4. Sub-THz MIMO antenna (a) Schematic view: front view (b) Return loss

A 2×4 MIMO array antenna was designed of size $2348.18 \times 1200 \times 80.8 \mu\text{m}^3$ with Polyimide substrate. The designed MIMO antenna was circular in shape from the three sides and converted to array with four elements. Gains of the antenna were 9.7 dBi with efficiencies 90.2 % 0.281 THz and 89.1 % at 0.282 THz. The schematic view and return loss were shown in the Figs 5 (a) and (b) below [67].

Figure 5. 2×4 MIMO array antenna :a) Schematic view b) S parameter

A V shaped antenna with defected ground structure (DGS) was designed to remove the drawbacks of CMOS microstrip patch antenna in the frequency range 0.22-0.32 THz and mostly used for wireless and imaging applications. Slots were formed in the ground to make it as defective ground which will increase radiation resistance for achieving high bandwidth and efficiency.

The leakage wave present in Si ($\epsilon_r = 11.68$, $h = 250 \mu\text{m}$ and $\tan\delta < 4 \times 10^{-5}$) substrate passed through the slots of ground and added in phase with wave coming from patch which will significantly improve gain and directivity. The reflection coefficient greater than -10 dB was obtained for fabricated antenna in the frequency range 0.24 THz to greater than 0.32 THz. The designed antenna possess bandwidth of 15.55% and a gain of 5.48 dBi at 0.295 THz is obtained with 28.7% efficiency. The schematic views and return loss for designed antenna and fabricated antenna are shown in Figs 6 (a), (b), (c) [68].

Figure 6. On chip antenna (a) Schematic view (b) Fabricated antenna (c) Reflection coefficient of designed antenna and fabricated antenna

3. Design of THz antennas for space applications

Various public and private agencies are trying to develop space links in order to provide communication between space and earth. So space traffic is increasing continuously and becoming a challenge to manage [69]. Previously free space optical communication (FSO) was used for space communication where optical links suffered lots of attenuation because of changing atmospheric conditions. Size of satellites are getting smaller day by day. THz transmitter and receiver antennas in the form of MIMO arrays with miniaturized dimensions are the new hope for space communication. Technology is becoming so advanced that spacecraft are

made smaller and easy to move to a place where they are needed [70].

An octagonal shaped antenna operating at 0.75-10 THz was used for large frequency range applications like in industries for inspection, astronomy and material characterization. Designed antenna used Rogers RT/Duroid 5880 as substrate ($\epsilon_r = 2.2$ and $\tan\delta = .0004$) and was operating in three frequency bands where the lower band covers 0.75-6.5 THz, medium band covers 6.75- 8.25 THz and upper frequency band covers 8.45 THz-10.25 THz. Dimensions of the designed antenna were shown in Figure 7(a) where S denotes each side of the patch having length $41.21\mu\text{m}$. L and W were the length and width of the substrate given by $160\mu\text{m}$ and $150\mu\text{m}$. The length of the ground plane L_g was $46\mu\text{m}$ and T_l and T_w were the length and width of the feed line having dimensions $50\mu\text{m}$ and $20\mu\text{m}$ respectively. The schematic view and return loss are shown in Figs 7 (a) and (b) [71].

Figure 7. Octagonal shaped patch antenna (I) Schematic view (II) Return loss

4. Design of THz antennas for defense applications

Antennas working on THz band are mostly used in national level defense applications. The screening of concealed weapons, explosives and persons can be done by using various THz imaging techniques.

An antenna designed for radar and for getting information of terrorists attack having gain 16.95 dB resonating. The original butterfly antenna is improved with fractal structure which increases gain and cost effectively. Antenna gives return loss of 33.59 dB for butterfly antenna with fractal structure which was -17.47 dB. The Schematic view and return loss comparison for ordinary butterfly antenna and with fractal geometry are shown in Figs 8 (a) and (b) given below [72].

Figure 8. Fractal butterfly antenna (a) Schematic view (b) Return loss

7. LOSSES AT THz FREQUENCY BAND

With the increase in distance, signal transmitted at THz frequency suffers from path loss. There are many factors

which affects the effective transmission at THz band. Presently experiments have been done in order to achieve efficient transmission on 300 GHz frequency [73]-[75]. Channels with lower transmit frequencies are unable to transmit at high frequency due to presence of very high path loss and reflection losses. Propagating waves also undergo absorption loss which, is due to different concentration of the molecules comes during transmission. The molecules present in the medium attenuate the signal and produces noise during transmission [76]. The total path loss in the THz frequency band is obtained by the addition of spreading loss and molecular absorption loss where both are expressed in dB [77]. It is given by equation (15).

$$A_{\text{spread}}(f, d)[\text{dB}] = A_{\text{spread}}(f, d)[\text{dB}] + A_{\text{abs}}(f, d)[\text{dB}]$$

where, d is the total path length and f is wave frequency.

The spreading loss occurs as a result of attenuation due to the expansion of a wave, as it propagates through the free-space loss medium [78]. This is defined in dB by equation (16).

$$A_{\text{spread}}(f, d)[\text{dB}] = 20\log\left(\frac{4\pi fd}{c}\right)$$

Due to unavoidable atmospheric conditions like rain, fog and pollution occurs during propagation of signal, data transmission is becoming a challenge for wireless technologies at more than 10 THz infrared frequencies. At very high frequencies the losses due to reflection of signals are more as well as alignment of transmitter and receiver is also a major problem for achieving high data rates [79].

8. VISION BEHIND THz

THz technology is growing at a very fast speed and evidences are available by the lot of publications and experiments which are undergoing in this area. Most of the companies started production of various instruments working on THz frequency in the field of imaging and spectroscopy. THz detectors and emitters are available nowadays but they are bulky and expensive. So, research is going on to reduce the price and the size for increasing its market value. Different technologies like MEMS, photonics crystals and use of metamaterial will definitely increase its demand in near future

9. CONCLUSION

The data transmission rates for wireless communication are increasing tremendously so, to catch up these rates THz transmission is becoming a new hope for users. For broadband communication. This paper covers the different frequency range lies in between 100 GHz to 10 THz. THz signal can be generated optically by means of photo diodes and photoconductors as well as electronically by means of oscillators. SBD and bolometers are used for detection. Different metals and non metals like copper, Graphene, CNT, silicon, Polyimide, PDMS, BCB, COC and Parylene are given in this paper which is used as substrate at different bands of THz frequency technologies adapted for the fabrication of antennas at THz band. Patch antennas with different geometries and different substrates are discussed here. MIMO antennas are also designed at this frequency band for achieving high gain. All the different types of THz

antennas are compared in Table 3 with respect to frequency bands, substrates, size, gain, efficiency and their applications.

Table 3: Comparison of THz antennas at different bands of frequency

Ref.	Frequency Bands (THz)	Substrate	Size (μm^2)	Gain (dBi)	Design	Applications
[66]	0.229-0.234 0.288-0.295	RT5880	1430 × 1400	7.7 8.69	MIMO	Wireless communication
[67]	0.2-0.4	Polyimide	2348.18 × 1200	9.7	MIMO	Wireless communication
[68]	0.22-0.32	Si	Not Available	5.48	Single element	Communication and imaging
[71]	0.75-10	RT5880	60×150	Not available	Single element	Astronomy and for inspection of materials
[72]	0.1-10	Graphene and gold	Adjustable with frequency	16.95	Single element	Defense applications

REFERENCES

- Monika Tuteja, Shally Gujral, Baljit Kaur. "Redefining wireless technology with spectral efficiency" International Journal of Innovative Science, Engineering and Technology. 1(4), pp. 257-263, 2014.
- Garg VK Wireless Communications and Networking. 1st Edition, US: 34. Elsevier, 2007.
- Parul Gupta, Leeladhar Malviya and S. V. Charate "5G multi-element/port antenna design for wireless applications a review". International Journal of Microwave and Wireless technologies. , vol. 11, pp. 918-938, 2019.
- Bliss DW and Govindasamy S. Adaptive Wireless Communications, 1st Edition. UK, Cambridge University Press, 2013.
- Dahlman E, Parkvall S and Skold J 4G, LTE/LTE-Advanced for Mobile Broadband, 2nd Edition Sweden, Elsevier, 2013.
- Mohit Pant, Leeladhar Malviya and Vineeta Choudhary "Gain and bandwidth enhancement of 28 GHz tapered feed antenna array" International Conference on Computing, Communication and Networking Technologies (ICCCNT). , pp. 1-4,2020.
- Mohit Pant, Leeladhar Malviya and Vineeta Choudhary "A 28 GHz Corporate series-fed taper antenna array for fifth generation wireless communication Mobile Radio Communications and 5G Networks" pp. 697-705,2020.
- Leevanshi Rao, Mohit Pant, Leeladhar Malviya, Ajay Parmar and Sandhya. Vijay Charhate "5G beamforming techniques for the coverage of intended directions in modern wireless communication" in-depth review. International Journal of Microwave and Wireless Technologies. pp. 1-24, 2020.
- S. Cherry. Edholm's law of bandwidth. IEEE Spectrum: , pp. 58-60, 2004.
- J. W. Fleming "High resolution submillimeter-wave Fourier-transform spectrometry of gases" IEEE Transactions Microwave Theory and Techniques. pp. 1023–1025,1974.
- Rohit Singh, Douglas Sicker "Analytical model for efficient indoor THz access point deployment" IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC) Seoul, South Korea. pp. 1-8, 2020.
- Tadao Nagatsuma. "Terahertz Technologies: present and future IECEI electronics express",pp. 1127-1142. July 2011.
- Marian Greconici, Gheorghe Madescu, and Martian Mot: "Skin effect analysis in a free space conductor, Facta universitatis – series" Electronics and Energetics. 2010, pp. 207-215.
- Jemima P. Stephen, Duraisamy Jude Hemanth "An investigation on specific absorption rate reduction materials with human tissue cube for biomedical applications" International Journal of RF and Microwave computer aided engineering. pp. 1-19, 2019.
- Dash S, Patnaik A "Dual band reconfigurable plasmonic antenna copper dipole antenna using bilayer Graphene". IEEE International Symposium on Antennas and propagation AP-S. pp. 921–922, 2017.
- Yasser Zare and Kyong Yop Rhee "A Simple and sensible equation for interphase potensy in carbon nano tubes reinforced (CNT) nanocomposites". Journal of Material Research and Technology, pp. 6488-6496, 2020.
- L.Zou, W. Withayachumnankul, C. M. Shah, A. Mitchell, M. Bhaskaran, S. Sriram, C.Fumeaux. "Dielectric resonator nanoantennas at visible frequencies". Optics Express. pp. 1344-1352, 2013..
- L. Zou, M. L'opez-Garc'ia, W. Withayachumnankul, C. M. Shah, A. Mitchell, M. Bhaskaran, S.Sriram, R. Oulton, M. Klemm, C. Fumeaux."Spectral and angular characteristics of dielectric resonator metasurface at optical frequencies" Applied Physics Letters. pp. 1-4,2014.
- MiaoLiu, JianrenSun, YingSun, Christopher Bockand Quanfang Chen. "Thickness-dependent mechanical properties of polydimethylsiloxane membranes. Journal of micromechanics and microengineering". pp. 1-6, 2009.
- Ako, Rajour Tanyi, Upadhyay, Adi; Withayachumnakul, Withawat "Dielectrics for Terahertz Metasurfaces: Material Selection and Fabrication Techniques" Advance Optical Materials, pp. 1-16, 2019.
- Sumeet Walia, Charan M. Shah, Philipp Gutruf, Hussein Nili, Dibakar Roy Chowdhury, Withawat Withayachumnankul, Madhu Bhaskaran, Sharath Sriram. "Flexible metasurfaces and metamaterials "A review of materials and fabrication processes at micro- and nano-scales. Applied Physics Reviews". pp. 1-15, 2015.
- A. J. Gatesman, J. Waldman, M. Ji, C. Musante, S. Yagvesson "An anti-reflection coating for silicon optics at terahertz frequencies". IEEE Microwave and Guided Wave Letters. pp. 264-266, 2000.
- E. Perret, N. Zerounian, S. David, F. Aniel "Complex permittivity characterization of benzocyclobutene for terahertz applications" Microelectronic Engineering. pp. 2276- 2281, 2008.

24. F. Pavanello, F. Garet, M.-B. Kuppam, E. Peytavit, M. Vanwolleghem, F. Vaurette, J.-L.Coutaz, J.-F. Lampin: "Broadband ultra-low-loss mesh filters on flexible cyclic olefin copolymer films for terahertz applications". *Applied Physics Letters*. , pp. 1-5, 2013.
25. H.Rucker, B. Heinemann. A. Fox."Half-Terahertz SiGe BiCMOS Technology" IEEE 12th Topical meeting on Silicon monolithic Integrated circuits in RF Systems, SiRF. pp. 133-136, 2012.
- 26.S. Voinigescu, A. Tomkins, E. dacquay ,P .Chevalier, JHasch, A.Chatre, B.Sautreuil " A study of SiGe HBT signal sources in the 220-330 GHz range" IEEE Journal on solid state circuits. 2013, pp. 1-11.
- 27.K.Shinohara D Regan, Y.Tang, A.Corrion, D.Brown, J.Wong, J.Robinson, H.Fung, A.Schmitz, T.oh., S.kim.p.chen, R.Nagele, "A Margomenous, M.Micovic: Scaling of gan HEMTs and schottky diodes for submillimeter wave mmic applications" IEEE Transactions in Electronics devices. pp. 2982-2996, 2013.
28. C. Campbell, M Kao, S .nayak. "High efficiency Ka band power amplifier with 0.15nm Gan on sic HEMT process" IEEE MTTs International Microwave Symposium Digest, , pp. 1-3, 2012.
- 29.M.Micovic, A.Kurdoghlian, A Margomenos, D. Brown, K.Shinohara, S. Burnham, I.Milosavljevic, R.Browen"A Williams, P.Hashimoto 92-96 GHz GaN Poer amplifiers". MTTs International Microwave Symposium Digest. pp. 1- 3, 2012.
- 30.V. Radisic, K.Leong, X.Mei, S.Sarkozy, W.Deal "Power amplification at 0.65 THz using inp HEMT's" IEEE Transactions on Microwave Theory and Techniques. pp. 724 – 729, 2011.
- 31.M.C.Wanke, MLee, C.D.Nordquist, M.J.Cich, M.Cavaliere, A.M.Rowen, J.R.Gillen, C.L.Arrington, A.D. Grine, C.T.Fuller, J.L. Reno."Integrated chip-scale THz technology". Society of photo-optical Instrumentation Engineers(SPIE). pp. 1-10. 2011.
- 32.T.Otsuji, T.Komori, T.Waanabe, T.Suemetsu. D. Coquillat, W.Knap" Plasmon resonant microchip emitters and detectors for Terahertz sensing and spectroscopic applications". Proceedings in The International Society for Optical Engineering (SPIE). pp. 2-12, 2012.
33. L.Vicarelli, M.S. Vitiello, D. Coquillat, A. Lombardo, A.C.Ferrari, W.Knap, M. pollini, V.pellegrini, A.Tredicucci "Graphene field effect transistors as room temperature terahertz detector nature materials" pp. 865-871, 2012.
- 34.K.Novoselov, .Geim, S.Morozov, D.Jiang, Y.S.V.Dubonos, I.V.Grigorieva, A.A.Firsov "Electric field effect in atomically thin carbon films, science" pp. 666-669, 2004.
35. A.K.Geim, K.Novoselov "The rise of Graphene. Nature matter", pp. 183-191, 2007.
36. H.-J.Song, K.Ajito, Y.Muramoto, A.Wakatsuki, Nagatsuma, and N. Kukutsu."24 Gbit/s data transmission in 300 GHz band for future Terahertz communications" *Electronics Letters*. pp. 953-954, 2012.
- 37.Leeladhar Malviya, MachaVaram Kartikeyan, Rajib K. Panigrahi" Offset planar MIMO antenna for omnidirectional radiation patterns". *International Journal of RF and microwave*. 2018, pp. 1-9.
- 38.Schiller J:Mobile Communications, 2nd Edition. UK Pearson, 2003.
- 39.Rappaport T. wireless communications: principles and practice. 2nd edition upper saddle river, nj :pearson, 2010,pp. 1-736.
40. Leeladhar Malviya, Rajib K. Panigrahi, and Machavaram V. Kartikeyan "Circularly Polarized 2 x 2 MIMO antenna for WLAN applications". *Progress In Electromagnetics Research C*. pp. 97–107, 2016.
41. Leeladhar Malviya, R. K. Panigrahi, and M. V. Kartikeyan: "2x2 MIMO antenna for ISM band application". *International Conference on Industrial and Information systems (ICIIS)*. , pp. 794-797, 2016.
42. Leeladhar Malviya, Rajib K. Panigrahi, and Machavaram V. Kartikeyan: "A 2x2 Dual-Band MIMO Antenna with Polarization Diversity for Wireless Applications". *Progress In Electromagnetics Research C*. pp. 91–103, 2016.
- 43.Leeladhar Malviya, Rajib Kumar Panigrahi, M.V. Kartikeyan: MIMO Antennas for Wireless Communication. 1st Edition, Publisher: CRC Press, ISBN: 9781003080275, 2020.
- 44.Leeladhar Malviya, R. K. Panigrahi and M. V. Kartikeyan: "Four Element Planar MIMO Antenna Design for Long-Term Evolution Operation". *IETE Journal of Research*. , pp. 367-373, 2017.
45. Singh, H.S. Pandey, G.K. Bharti, P.K. Meshram, M.K." A compact dual-band diversity antenna for WLAN applications with high isolation". *Microwave and optical technology letters*. pp. 906–912, 2015.
46. Leeladhar Malviya, M.V. Kartikeyan, R. K. Panigrahi: "Offset planar MIMO antenna for omnidirectional radiation patterns" *International Journal of RF and Microwave*. , pp.1-10, 2018.
47. Leeladhar Malviya, Rajib Kumar Panigrahi and M. V. Kartikeyan "MIMO antennas with diversity and mutual coupling reduction techniques: a review". *International Journal of Microwave and Wireless Technologies*. pp. 1763–1780, 2017.
48. J.H. Son"Terahertz Biomedical Science and Technology" Seoul, CRC Press, 2014.
49. Sanjay Chouhan and Leeladhar Malviya"Two element folded meander line MIMO antenna for Wireless applications" *ELECTRONICS* . pp. 11-17, 2019.
50. Lin J."Specific absorption rates (SARs) induced in head tissues by microwave radiation from cell phones" *IEEE Antennas and wave Propagation Magazine*. 2000, pp. 138-139.
51. Leeladhar Malviya and Sanjay Chouhan" Multi-cut four-port shared radiator with ground and diversity effects for WLAN application". *International Journal of Microwave and Wireless technologies*. pp. 1-10, 2019.
- 52.Mushtaq AB and Kumar V.: Calculation of SAR and measurement of temperature change of human head due to the mobile phone waves at frequencies 900 MHz and

- 1800 MHz Advances in Physics Theories and Applications 2013, pp. 54-63.
53. Kim KW, Rahmat - Samii Y.: Handset antennas and humans at Ka-band: the importance of directional antennas. IEEE Transactions on Antennas and Propagation. 1998, 949-950.
 54. Dutta PK, Jayasree PVY, Baba VSSNS: SAR reduction in the modelled human head for the mobile phone using different material shields. Human Centric Computing and Information Sciences. 2016, 1-22.
 55. Chan KH, Chow KM, Fung LC, Leung SW. "Effects of using conductive materials for SAR reduction in mobile phones". Microwave Optical Technology Letters. 2004, pp. 140-144.
 56. Hossain MI, Faruque MRI, Islam MT "A new design of cell phone body for the SAR reduction in the human head" ACES Journal. 2015, pp. 792-798.
 57. Manapati M, Kshetrimayum R "SAR reduction in human head from mobile phone radiation using single negative metamaterials" Journal of Electromagnetic Waves and Applications. pp. 1385-1395, 2009.
 58. Wilke I. "Biological and pathological effects of 2.45 GHz on cells, fertility, brain and behavior". Umwelt Medizin Gesellschaft. 2018, pp. 1-32.
 59. Jemima P. Stephen and Duraisamy Jude Hemanth: An investigation on specific absorption rate reduction materials with human tissue cube for biomedical applications. International Journal of RF and Microwave computer aided engineering. 2019, pp. 1-19.
 60. Hardell L."World Health Organization, radio frequency radiation and health—a hard nut to crack (review)."Int J Oncology. pp. 405-413, 2017.
 61. Haridim M."Use of rod reflectors for SAR reduction in human head" IEEE Transactions on Electromagnetic Compatibility. pp. 40-46, 2016.
 62. J.H. Son: Terahertz Biomedical Science and Technology, Seoul, CRC Press, 2014.
 63. G. Geetharamani and T. Aathmanesan "Metamaterial inspired THz antenna for breast cancer detection", pp. 1-9, 2019.
 64. M. A. Jamshed, F. Heliot, and T. Brown "A survey on electromagnetic risk assessment and evaluation mechanism for future wireless communication systems" IEEE Journal of Electromagnetics RF and Microwaves in Medicine and Biology, pp. 8204-8250, 2020.
 65. A. Nauman, Y. A. Qadri, M. Amjad, Y. B. Zikria, M. K.A fzal, and S. W. Kim: Multimedia Internet of Things: A Comprehensive Survey, IEEE Access, 2020, pp. 8202–8250.
 66. Sneha Moghe, Leeladhar Malviya" Sub-THz high efficiency MIMO antenna for short range wireless communication" International conference on communication system and network technologies. pp. 66-71, 2022.
 67. Sneha Moghe, Rohit Yadav and Leeladhar Malviya"Sub-Terahertz MIMO Array Antenna for Future Wireless Applications" International conference on communication system and network technologies. pp. 49-53, 2022.
 68. Hyeongjin Kim, Wonseok Choe and Jinho Jeong" A Terahertz CMOS V shaped patch Antenna with DGS" (Basel, Switzerland), pp. 1-13, 2018.
 69. Meltem Civasl and Ozgur B. Akan" Terahertz wireless communication in space" ITU Journal on future and evolving technologies, pp. 1-8, 2021.
 70. Hemani Kaushal and Georges Kaddoum"Optical communication in space" challenges and mitigation techniques. IEEE communications surveys and tutorials, pp. 57– 96, 2016.
 71. G. Harika, G. Ventaka Subbaiah, Praveen V. Naidu, K. Rohini : A Compact Octagon Shaped Patch Antenna for Terahertz Applications. Journal of Innovative and Exploring Engineering. 2019 , pp. 2373 -2375.
 72. Yi shi, xiaodong zhang, qinxi qiu, yinrui gao, zhiming huang: Design of Terahertz Detection Antenna With Fractal Butterfly Structure IEEE Access, 2021, pp. 113823-113831.
 73. C. Jansen, S. Priebe, C. Moiler, M. Jacob, H. Dierke, M. Koch, T. Kurner: Diffuse Scattering from rough surfaces in THz communication channels, IEEE Transactions on Terahertz science and Technology. 2011, pp. 462-472.
 74. S. Priebe, M. Kaannicht, M. Jacob, T. Kurner.: Ultra Broadband Indoor channel measurements and calibrated ray tracing propagation modelling at THz frequencies. Journal of communication networks. 2013, pp. 547-558.
 75. S. Priebe, T. Kurner.: Stochastic Modelling of THz Indoor radio channels. IEEE Transactions on Wireless communication. 2013,; 12(9): pp. 4445-4455.
 76. S. Priebe, C. Jastrow, M. Jacob, T. Kleine-Ostmann, T. Schrader, T. Kurner.: Channel and propagation measurements at 300 GHz. IEEE transactions on Antenna and propagation. 2011, pp. 1688-1698.
 77. R.M. Goody Y.L. Yung; Atmospheric Radiation: Theoretical Basis, 2nd edition Oxford University press 1989.
 78. Josep Miquel Jornet, Ian F. Akyildiz "Channel Modeling and Capacity Analysis for Electromagnetic Wireless Nanonetworks in the Terahertz Band" IEEE Transactions on wireless communications. pp. 3211-3221, 2011.
 79. M. Koch; Terahertz communications: a 2020 vision, in :R. Miles, X C. Zhang, H. Eisele, A. Krotkus. "Terahertz Frequency detection and identification of Materials and objects in: NATO Security through science series" Springer. pp. 325-338, 2007.